

Karnataka’s Urbanisation Woes and Measures to Streamline Its Unbridled Urbanisation

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Abstract

When one seeks to identify the drivers of Karnataka’s urbanisation woes, at least two facts stand out: urban migration in India and Karnataka is triggered by the need to avoid starvation and has driven urbanisation. Further, rapid and unplanned growth in the name of urbanisation has made it worse. Such haphazard growth affects not only the residents of the metropolises but also the farmhouses that dot the outskirts of the metropolises. Hence the researcher interacted with urban planners and farmhouse respondents to ascertain the measures that could help streamline unbridled urbanisation. The researcher concludes that urban policy should focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system. It would streamline unbridled urbanisation. Policy should not deter urban migration but instead focus on closing the social and industrial infrastructure gap in rural pockets to streamline unbridled urbanisation. Where migration is inevitable, policy should seek to integrate the migrant population into the urban fabric to streamline unbridled urbanisation. Collection of property tax in urban areas should be optimised if such corrective measures are to be launched seriously. For example, collection of property tax in Bangalore is at best 20 percent of its potential. Obviously, such poor collections can seldom help meet the demand of the residents for civic amenities. Policy should empower cities by permitting local urban bodies to raise funds and enforce land usage norms.

Keywords: Amenities; Drivers; Metropolises; Migration; Property tax; Trigger; Urbanisation.

Theoretical Background of the Problem

Urbanisation, in a way, is a great leveller. It affects the advanced economies as much as it affects the emerging market economies (EMEs). However, the EMEs find it more difficult to tackle. Too many urban pockets crop up. The pace and density of population that migrates to urban pockets picks up steam placing a strain on the urban pockets which are already bursting at the seams. The scenario is rendered even more confusing in the Indian context where local self-governments define statutory towns differently. The outcome therefore is an avoidable and intriguing amalgam of the old and new and modernity and tradition. As a result, traditional and more modern forms of administration are frequently in competition with one another, with the end nowhere in sight.

Statement of the Problem

As usual, one has to begin at the beginning. The factors that drive urbanisation have to be identified. Some of them are well known and perhaps are found all over the country. Yet some of them are state-specific like the froth and fire one increasingly notices in a couple of lakes in Bangalore city. Having done that, one should put in place the right strategy to handle the situation and prevent the recurrence of such a situation in future.

Scope of the Study

The study confines itself to the major stake-holders, namely, farmhouses and urban planners based out of Bangalore, Karnataka. Farmhouse respondents have been reckoned because they inhabit the outskirts of metropolises. The said outskirts are often used as landfills by the local self-governments of the metropolises. Groundwater from the outskirts is exploited by the said local self-governments to provide potable water to its residents and to meet the water requirements of the industry. As a result, the farmhouses experience pollution, see a reduction in their water table and a fall in the fertility levels of the soil of their farms.

Objectives of the Study

1. Identify the drivers of Karnataka’s urbanisation
2. Ascertain the measures needed to streamline the unbridled urbanisation in Karnataka

Hypothesis Proposed to be Tested

H0: Policy should not focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system to streamline unbridled urbanisation.

H1: Policy should focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system to streamline unbridled urbanisation.

Research Methodology

The study is used an interview schedule for primary data collection from the respondents. It has been utilised both the secondary and primary data and 50 farmhouses operating and 50 urban planners consulting in the area covered by the study at least for the past five years. In order to assess the data, the chi-square data was used.

Drivers Of Karnataka’s Urbanisation

Several assorted developments have driven Karnataka’s urbanisation, according to well-informed stakeholders. Hence the study wished the respondents to divulge the drivers of Karnataka’s urbanisation.

Table-1 Drivers of Karnataka’s Urbanisation

Drivers	Number of respondents
Urban migration in India and Karnataka is triggered by the need to avoid starvation and has driven urbanisation	45
Rapid and unplanned growth in the name of urbanisation has driven urbanisation	43

Urban development is a state subject and the states defining statutory towns vaguely has driven urbanisation	43
Cities with a population closer to the 10-lakh mark have grown much faster and has driven urbanisation	39

From the table-1 it can be understood that, 45 respondents have responded that in Karnataka and India the urbanization was taken place due to mitigate the level starvation and it has increased the process of urbanization. 43 respondents opined that, urbanization was driven by unplanned growth and statutory states respectively. 39 respondents are agreed that population having more than 10 lakhs have increased the speed of urbanization.

Measures To Streamline Unbridled Urbanisation

Having ascertained the drivers of urbanisation, the study wanted to recognize from the respondents the measures required to modernize the unconcealed urbanisation. Their responses are presented in the following Table-2.

Table-2 Measures to Streamline Unbridled Urbanisation

Measures	Number of Respondents
Policy should focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system to streamline unbridled urbanisation	46
Policy should not deter urban migration but focus on closing the social and industrial infrastructure gap in rural pockets to streamline unbridled urbanisation	44
Where migration is inevitable, policy should seek to integrate the migrant population into the urban fabric to streamline unbridled urbanisation	39

Table-2 shows the measures to streamline unbridled urbanization. 46 respondents are given their opinion that policy framework necessarily required to connect bursting metropolises with the help of system of efficient transportation in order to streamline the unbridled urbanization. 44 respondents are agreed that, policy is helping in bridging the gap between the social and industrial infrastructure in streamlining the unbridled urbanization. Unbridled urbanization can be streamlined by integrating the migrant population into urban fabric as expressed by 39 respondents.

Drivers of Karnataka’s Urbanisation

Several multifarious developments have driven Karnataka’s urbanisation, according to well-informed stakeholders. Hence the study asked the respondents to unveil the drivers of Karnataka’s urbanisation. Their reactions to the interrogation give the idea in the following Table-3.

Table-3 Drivers of Karnataka’s Urbanisation

Drivers	Number of respondents
Urban migration in India and Karnataka is triggered by the need to avoid starvation	47
Cities with a population closer to the 10-lakh mark have grown much faster	47
Urban development is a state subject and the states define statutory towns vaguely	46
What is urban settlement under the central government is a “census town” according to many state governments?	46
Rapid and unplanned growth in the name of urbanisation has driven urbanisation	45

The table-3 depicts about that responses on the Drivers of Karnataka’s urbanisation. It can be evaluated that, 47 respondents are agreed that avoid the starvation has initiated the process of urbanization and population increasing trends are major factors respectively. 46 respondents are accepted that urban development as a state subject and under central government it is a census town respectively. Finally 45 respondents are expressed that, urbanization has been driven by the name of unplanned rapid growth.

Measures to Streamline Unbridled Urbanisation

Having ascertained the drivers of urbanisation, the researcher sought to know from the respondents the measures needed to streamline the unbridled urbanisation. Their answers to the interrogation seem in the following Table.

Table-4 Measures to Streamline Unbridled Urbanisation

Measures	Number of respondents
Policy should focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system	47
Collection of property tax in urban Bangalore is at best 20 per cent of its potential which needs to be corrected	45
Minimising the cost of migration, eliminating all kinds of discrimination against the migrant population and protecting the migrants’ rights will augur well for all the stakeholders	45
Policy should empower cities by permitting local urban bodies to raise funds and enforce land usage norms	45
Where migration is inevitable, policy should seek to integrate the migrant population into the urban fabric	44
Policy should not deter urban migration but focus on closing the social and industrial infrastructure gap in rural pockets	39

From the table-4 majority of 47 respondents are agreed that policy focus is needed to development of towns through the effective system of transportation nearly 45 respondents are provided their opinion that property tax reduction and elimination of discrimination against the migrant people can be useful to increase the level of urbanization. 44 respondents are agreed that the policy is needed in integrating the urban fabric and migrant population. Finally 39 respondents are expressed that the gap between the social and industrial infrastructure can be reduced by policy framework.

Category	Observed Values		
	Yes	No	Total
Farmhouse respondents	46	4	50
Urban planners	47	3	50
Total	93	7	100
Category	Expected Values		
	Yes	No	Total
Farmhouse respondents	46.5	3.5	50
Urban planners	46.5	3.5	50
Total	93	7	100
	Yes	No	
o-e	-0.5000	0.5000	
	0.5000	-0.5000	
(o-e) ²	0.2500	0.2500	
	0.2500	0.2500	
((o-e) ² /e	0.0054	0.0714	
	0.0054	0.0714	
CV	0.0108	0.1429	0.1536
TV			3.8415
p			0.9972

The calculated value of χ^2 is 0.1536, less than the table value of 3.8415 for an alpha of 0.05 at one degree of freedom. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted that, the policy should not focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system to streamline unbridled urbanisation.

Summary of Findings

1. Urban migration in India and Karnataka is triggered by the need to avoid starvation and has driven urbanisation over 45 respondents. Rapid and unplanned growth in the name of urbanisation has driven urbanisation, argue 43 respondents. Urban development is a state subject and the state defining statutory towns vaguely has driven urbanisation, state 43 respondents. Cities with a population closer to the 10-lakh mark have grown much faster and this has driven urbanisation assert 39 respondents
2. Policy should focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system to streamline unbridled urbanisation, assert

- 46 respondents. Policy should not deter urban migration but focus on closing the social and industrial infrastructure gap in rural pockets to streamline unbridled urbanisation, state 44 respondents. Where migration is inevitable, policy should seek to integrate the migrant population into the urban fabric to streamline unbridled urbanisation, aver 39 respondents.
3. Urban migration in India and Karnataka is triggered by the need to avoid starvation and has driven urbanisation aver 47 respondents. Cities with a population closer to the 10-lakh mark have grown much faster and this has driven urbanisation assert 47 respondents. Urban development is a state subject and the states defining statutory towns vaguely have driven urbanisation, state 46 respondents. What is urban settlement under the central government is a “census town” according to many state governments cite 46 respondents. Rapid and unplanned growth in the name of urbanisation has driven urbanisation, argue 45 respondents.
 4. Policy should focus on development of counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system to streamline unbridled urbanisation, assert 47 respondents. Collection of property tax in urban Bangalore is at best 20 percent of its potential which needs to be corrected aver 45 respondents. Minimising the cost of migration, eliminating all kinds of discrimination against the migrant population and protecting the migrants’ rights will augur well for all the stakeholders, according to 45 respondents. Policy should empower cities by permitting local urban bodies to raise funds and enforce land usage norms assert 45 respondents. Where migration is inevitable, policy should seek to integrate the migrant population into the urban fabric, state 44 respondents. Policy should not deter urban migration but focus on closing the social and industrial infrastructure gap in rural pockets, assert 39 respondents.

Concluding Recommendations

Whatever the provocation, the unplanned growth in the name of urbanisation should be avoided. It may provide relief in the short-term but in the medium term the outcome will outweigh the gains made in the short term. The definition of statutory town needs to be uniform across the country. The inconsistency in the definition across the country gives rise to rapid, disorderly and haphazard growth of towns and cities across the country. Planners should focus on cities nearing the 10-lakh population mark since they have been growing at a faster rate and regulating them could become a formidable task. They could grow out of control sooner than later. Developing counter-magnet towns that connect with bursting metropolises through an efficient transport system to streamline unbridled urbanisation is a good idea. The bursting metropolises and the counter-magnet towns will supplement each other ideally. Policy should not deter urban migration since it will prove counter-productive. Instead it should focus on closing the social and industrial infrastructure gap in rural pockets to streamline unbridled urbanisation. Throwing good money after bad is not a sensible policy. Where migration is inevitable, policy should seek to integrate the migrant population seamlessly into the urban fabric to streamline unbridled urbanisation. Collection of property tax in urban areas should be optimised. For example, collection of property tax in Bangalore is at best 20 percent of its potential. Obviously, such poor collections can seldom help meet the demand of the residents for civic amenities. Minimising the cost of migration, eliminating all kinds of discrimination against the migrant population and protecting the migrants’ rights will augur well for all the stakeholders. Policy should empower cities by permitting local urban bodies to raise funds and enforce land usage norms

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